

PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYMENT AND POOR REDUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *In this article, the world economy today is characterized by such processes as the aggravation of various financial, economic, socio-political crises, the limitation of socio-economic relations between countries as a result of various trade wars between countries. As a result, many national economies around the world have experienced slowing GDP growth, declining real incomes, deepening social stratification and rising poverty.*

Key words: *poverty, employment and income, living wage, consumer basket, gross domestic product, minimum wage, unemployment.*

Today, at a time when the world seems to be stalling because of the coronavirus, let's start our speech with questions as a joke.

Why are there so many poor, helpless people on our planet? There is no money. Why are diseases so common in our country? There is no money. Why are the seas drying up, the oceans polluting, and the lands becoming unusable? There is no money. Why do we have a high level of illiteracy? There is no money.

Is money really the solution to all problems? No, of course not.

Oscar Wilde, a British writer and poet, said, "The poorest class in society is the one who thinks more about money than the rich. After all, they have nothing to think about but money. That's the problem with poverty".

Today, the world economy is characterized by such processes as the intensification of various financial and economic, socio-political crises, the limitation of socio-economic relations between countries as a result of the escalation of various trade wars between countries. As a result, many of the world's national economies are experiencing a slowdown in GDP growth, declining real incomes, deepening social stratification and rising poverty.

Poverty is the inability to provide a certain acceptable standard of living. In short, it is the level of basic needs of a particular person or family that exceeds their ability to satisfy them.

Focusing on the quality and conditions of life allows us to determine the difference between a person's (or family's) social status and his or her standard of living.

Today, poverty, which is an urgent manifestation of poverty, remains one of the biggest and perhaps the most painful problems in the world. Poverty means a person lives on \$ 1.90 a day or less. At the same time, poverty is a reflection of the fact that a person has an income below the poverty line and that a person lives with nothing. Although the poverty line is set at \$ 1.90 a day, each country sets a poverty line based on its level of development and capabilities. For example, in EU countries, if a person's income is less than 60% of the average wage in the country where he or she lives, he or she is considered poor. In most countries of the world, the poverty line is defined as the income limit below the subsistence level.

There is no mention of the living wage in Uzbekistan yet. In most countries of the world, this concept is widely used in practice. In our country, the term “poor” is used instead of “poverty” and “poverty”. The calculation of the subsistence minimum will lead to the expansion of the tasks assigned to the state in the field of social protection.

The subsistence minimum is the cost of the consumer basket, which includes the minimum set of food products, non-food goods and services necessary to maintain human health and ensure his life, as well as mandatory payments and fees. In other words, the subsistence minimum reflects the limit at which the most basic human needs cannot be met or poverty is replaced by poverty.

Simply put, the consumer basket is the smallest set of products, goods and services necessary to maintain human life and health for a certain period of time. Everyone has to pay for food, clothing, utilities and other services, buy necessary medicines, and so on. All this is the basis for assembling a basket of products. Its data, in turn, is used to determine the minimum amount needed to exist (the value of the consumer basket).

The consumer basket should be the basis for calculating the quantity:

- 1) the minimum wages and pensions;
- 2) basic social benefits: unemployment, childcare, survivor benefits, scholarships, etc.

The range of goods and services included in the consumer basket varies from country to country. Its composition is determined at the state level and depends on many factors - natural and climatic conditions, economic development of the country, characteristics of food production, actual consumption of goods and services, and other factors.

The living wage is a very important indicator. It is widely used in determining the size of the minimum wage, pensions and benefits, calculating state and local budgets, and developing social programs.

In 2019, Uzbekistan ranked 49th in the world, gaining 10.7 points in the global hunger index.

The Global Hunger Index (GHI) is published annually by Concern Worldwide and Welthungerhilfe, an international non-governmental organization. Estimates are made in a three-step process based on data from various sources.

Four indicators are used to calculate the global hunger index for each country:

1. Malnutrition: The proportion of the population that is undernourished (ie, low in calories).

2. Childhood malnutrition: the proportion of children under five years of age who are malnourished (ie, their height does not match their body weight as a result of malnutrition).

3. Stunting in children: the proportion of children under five years of age with stunted growth (ie, the fact that children are stunted relative to their age indicates that they are chronically malnourished).

4. Child mortality: the rate of death of children under five years of age as a result of factors such as malnutrition and an unhealthy environment.

In the study, each of the four indicators is rated on a 100-point scale, based on the highest indicators on a global scale over the past decade. If a country scored between 0 and 10 points, it means that the country has a “low hunger rate”. A score of 10 to 19.9 indicates “moderate hunger,” a score of 20 to 34.9 indicates “severe hunger,” and a score of 35 to 49.9 indicates “critical hunger.” A score of 50 or more indicates that the country's hunger is on a “catastrophic” scale.

Then the situation in Uzbekistan (10.7 points) indicates the level of “average hunger”.

Neighboring Kazakhstan ranks 20th, Kyrgyzstan 35th, and Turkmenistan 54th.

The share of such a population in our country in 2018 was very large - 62.1%. The lack of a modern methodology for the statistical study of poverty does not allow us to fully understand the problem and take appropriate measures in this regard.

The poverty rate does not fully reflect the situation. It does not reflect the degree of income stratification among members of society. In this case, extensive use of the Gini coefficient is recommended. The Gini coefficient was developed in 1912 by the Italian statistician Corrado Gini, often referred to as the "income concentration index" or "equity index", and shows the uneven distribution of income between different segments of the population. The ratio ranges from 0 (or 0%) to 1 (or 100%), where 0 represents absolute equality and 1 represents absolute inequality. The line of absolute equality does not occur in life: some people are rich and others are poor. Consequently, their income is not commensurate with their position in society.

In 2018, the incomes of the richest 10% of the population accounted for 23.7% of all incomes, while the incomes of the 10% of the population with low incomes accounted for only 3.9% of total income. We see that the decile income stratification ratio was 6.1. The size of the shadow economy in the economy of our country (according to the World Bank, this figure reaches 51%) does not allow us to calculate the data with extreme accuracy.

Articles 22-25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights read: “Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; to exercise their rights in the social and cultural spheres, to have a standard of living necessary for health and well-being, belonging to oneself and one's family, including clothing, food, medical care and necessary social services; have a standard of living necessary to ensure the health and well-being of the family, including clothing, food, medical care and necessary social services, as well as a lack of livelihood due to unemployment, illness, disability, widowhood, old age or other circumstances; in other cases ". Therefore, we have every reason to say that the fight against poverty is one of the important tasks of any democratic state.

It should be noted, however, that the allocation of large sums of money from various sources for poverty reduction alone is not enough. While poverty is extremely multifaceted, its causes are varied as well. The experience of past years clearly shows that poverty cannot be reduced

simply by increasing the allocated pensions, creating new jobs, improving the living conditions of the population, and increasing the amount of loans provided to businesses.

In particular, although the volume of loans issued to businesses over the past 2.5 years in our country is much higher than the amount of funds allocated over the past 30 years, this did not have a sufficiently positive impact.

The European Poverty Alleviation Network (EAPN) identifies a number of factors that increase the risk of falling into poverty. In particular, these factors include: unemployment, low literacy, disability, poor human health, belonging to a particular ethnic group, living in remote or poor areas, etc.

In our opinion, the most important aspect that should be paid attention to is the level of economic thinking of people. People should have a desire to make and improve their lives. They should feel protected and not afraid that their property will be destroyed or taken away by officials or businessmen close to the government. They must have institutions to ensure that their voices are always heard by the authorities, not just at the start of an election campaign. People should be provided with decent jobs, housing, medical and other similar social services.

In the fight against poverty, it is important to study the experience of countries around the world and apply it in practice. In particular, the use of the Chinese experience in the development of programs to combat poverty in Uzbekistan will have a positive effect. China has done a lot today to end poverty. According to the World Bank, today 850 million people in China have lifted themselves out of poverty. In China, the poverty rate was 88% in 1981, up from 0.7% in 2019. This indicator is fully consistent with the level of poverty in developed countries. Specifically, the poverty rate is 1% in the US, 0.61% in Sweden, 0.19% in Germany and 1.5% in Italy.

Poverty reduction measures in China are characterized by the following aspects:

1. Purposefulness of the specified measures of social protection;
2. Full support of research work on food security, providing local markets with quality food;
3. Approach to poverty alleviation based on the specifics of each region;
4. The social policy pursued in China is aimed at covering the interests of different segments of the population. In particular, while the goal is to

improve the quality of appropriate social services for the elderly, realizing the labor potential of the able-bodied, and especially young people, is at the heart of China's anti-poverty policy. The main emphasis is on vocational training for young people, that is, strict adherence to the teachings of Confucius: "People need to be given fishing rods and taught to fish";

5. Introduction of industrial production in rural areas with the aim of reducing poverty in rural areas, strengthening cooperation between agricultural producers;

6. Wide use of the practice of creating special economic zones for the purpose of socio-economic development of regions, increasing employment and incomes of the population;

7. Establish strict control over the spending of funds allocated to social programs.

Almost 46% of the world's population (3.4 billion people) live on less than \$ 5.5 a day, according to the World Bank's Poverty Reduction Report, which is published every two years. More than 1.9 billion people (26.2% of the world's population) live on less than \$ 3.2 a day. Although the share of the world's poorest living on \$ 1.90 a day has dropped to 10% globally, the problem of reducing global poverty has not yet lost its relevance.

According to Oxfam, for every dollar of tax revenue collected around the world, the tax paid by the rich is only 4 cents. If only the richest 1% of people in the world increase their taxes by just 0.5%, this will open access to school for 262 million children worldwide who are currently without basic schooling.

When thinking about poverty, it should be noted that there is a mechanism called the “poverty trap” when describing poverty and misery. There are a number of “poverty traps” that you can fall into. Here is some of them:

1. Being born and living in a poor country. The low level of economic development, in turn, leads to a deterioration in the quality of education, the quality of medical services provided is not up to the level of demand. This situation is characterized by low wages and high unemployment rates. In this case, the only way out of the trap is labor migration. According to the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the unemployment rate in Uzbekistan is 9.3% of the economically active population. Today the number of unemployed and promising people in our country is 1.3 million.

Data from the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations show that youth unemployment is high. In particular, unemployment among persons aged 20-30 was 15.1%, unemployment among persons aged 15-25 - 16.8%, and among women - 12.7%.

According to the data, today more than 4.5 million citizens of our country are employed abroad. Labor migrants send over \$ 5 billion to our country a year, which is more than 10% of the country's GDP. According to the World Bank, if the remittances of labor migrants fall sharply, the level of poverty in our country will double.

2. Birth and living in the countryside. It is no secret that the city provides its citizens with a high-quality standard of living. Compared to the rural population, urban dwellers have a number of advantages in terms of education, culture, medical services and high wages. Low incomes for rural populations prevent them from taking advantage of a number of development gains. Cities account for 75% of Uzbekistan's GDP and over 85% of industrial production. Cities account for 99.1% of information and communication services, 98.3% of financial services, 80.8% of educational services and 71.9% of medical services provided in the country.

3. Early childbearing and having many children. Because young women are unable to find work after the birth of their children, they are often trapped in poverty. If they are not educated enough, the situation becomes more complicated. As a result of the lack of an adequate level of education and practical work skills, women are deprived of the opportunity to get decent work and wages. The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) estimates that only 17% of families with children receive childcare benefits, but the benefits do not have a significant impact on poverty reduction. The poverty level among children under 15 is 1.5 times higher than among adults.

4. To be born into a poor family and not get a good education. Experts from the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) say that low-income families face serious financial difficulties in creating opportunities for their children to receive appropriate vocational and higher education. The fact that children from low-income families are currently deprived of such opportunities limits their future financial opportunities.

5. Work for a long time in a low-paid job. If a person is engaged in one activity for a long period of time, he gradually loses his skills and abilities.

While a person has been working in one place for a long time, the desire to make any positive changes in his life will gradually fade away.

According to a study by the Center for Analysis of Income and Living Standards of the Higher School of Economics, the behavior of people belonging to the poor changes over certain years in the following order: it strives to maintain the level of consumption and quality. life, trying to find a new or additional job, using all his strength and capabilities.

The next stage will last two years. At this stage, poor people begin to change their consumption patterns. It will start buying cheaper goods, replacing expensive overseas tourist trips with cheap domestic destinations. However, food consumption will remain at the same level.

If people who have fallen into poverty cannot find a decent job even after three years and have not started their own business, they will now start looking for other, even criminal, ways of earning a living. They cut consumption drastically.

By the seventh year of poverty, a person is getting used to his position, and now it is very difficult to return him to the sphere of productive labor. He prefers to retire, rely on the help of relatives, rather than go to work or engage in temporary income-generating activities.

When we talk about poverty, we must understand that this is not a one-man problem. Poverty gives rise to a number of negative processes in society and the economy. Poverty leads to an increase in the birth rate for a number of objective and subjective reasons. Because the poor lack access to adequate education, they join the ranks of low-skilled and unskilled workers. Professionals needed by society, especially teachers and doctors, are forced to leave their jobs and engage in other activities in order to receive a higher income. Poverty leads to an increase in crime as people are also forced to use illegal means of earning a living. Poverty leads to a sharp stratification of incomes in society and deep-rooted social conflicts.

American economist Jeffrey Sachs in his book "The End of Poverty" identifies six types of capital that allow society to break out of the grip of poverty: human capital, business capital, infrastructure, natural capital, social capital, and knowledge capital.

According to Sachs, the state should focus all its efforts on human capital (health, education, nutrition), infrastructure (roads, utilities, drinking water, environmental protection and sanitation), natural capital (biodiversity) and ecosystem conservation). socially established capital

(good governance, judiciary, law enforcement) and knowledge capital (support for research in various fields and sectors that serve the development of society).

We can increase the amount of funds allocated by the state for poverty reduction, attract entrepreneurs to a wide range of charitable activities, providing them with various benefits and benefits. However, the implementation of such measures practically cannot eliminate the problem of poverty in society. While such measures create the basis for the survival of the population, they simply cannot escape the clutches of poverty.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that the best way to combat poverty in our country is to change the economic thinking of citizens. It is very difficult to get out of the poverty trap without changing the economic thinking and economic education of citizens. As Jalaliddin Rumi said: “I used to be smart - I wanted to change the world. Now I am wise - I am changing.

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